

PRACTICAL USE OF METHODOLOGICAL TECHNIQUES IN THE ORGANIZATION OF HOME READING

Nasibboyeva Mukarrama Salimjon kizi

Assistant professor of the Department of social, humanitarian and specialty sciences, Andijan faculty of Tashkent Institute of Finance, Andijan, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8398196>

Abstract: The question that we are considering in this article - the role of home reading in teaching a foreign language and its organization in foreign language lessons - is one of the most relevant today. I would like to make a reservation right away, the concept of home reading is reading a work in a foreign language in the original. It seems to us that only the language of artistic works, conforming, as a rule, to the norms of modern literary language, is an irreplaceable model when learning a foreign language, and the role of this sample is especially great, since the language is studied outside the aisles of the secondary linguistic community. Reading a book written in such a language, a pupil has the opportunity to observe the existence of language in the speech of the author and his characters, follow the ways of expressing thoughts in a foreign language and directly perceive the meaning of what is being read. The book also creates a support for visual perception of the message, which is especially important for those who have visual perception developed better than auditory.

Key words: speaking, communicative orientation of learning, foreign language, material for independent conclusions and generalizations, translation, mental operations, development of oral speech skills, linguistic units, home reading.

Being an irreplaceable and inexhaustible source of diverse extralinguistic information, literary works expand the general horizons of students and, by providing material for independent conclusions and generalizations, creates a natural basis for the development of their thinking. Touching upon the most interesting and topical issues of our time, covering historical events, being rich in plot associations, a literary work does not cause only mental operations, but requires "going out" into communication, and therefore is also the basis for the development of oral speech skills, because it creates psychological prerequisites for speaking, communicative orientation of learning.

The object of the work is the process of organizing home reading in foreign language lessons.

The subject of the work is the organization of home reading in English lessons in higher school.

The purpose of the work is to identify effective forms and methods of organizing home reading, as one of the aspects of teaching English, taking into account the age characteristics of students.

Until quite recently, reading was given little importance in the system of teaching a foreign language. And if earlier it was believed that reading was only a source of new words entering the student's vocabulary and a starting point for a variety of statements of a dialogical and monological nature; now reading has become perceived as one of the main goals of learning - a source of new intellectual and aesthetic information that will significantly

enrich the student's personality if the learning process develops he has the ability and habit to use this source.

Reading today is the most realistic form of using the language competence acquired at school. In order to apply the oral speech skills acquired at school, the student needs at least one interlocutor with whom he will meet regularly, which is very problematic in our conditions. A student of any school (gymnasium, lyceum) can do this independently, one-on-one with a book, magazine, newspaper, and this will open up new prospects for him in educational, professional and personal improvement. But presented to himself, he will read in a foreign language only if it is not a difficult task for him (in other words, if he has a sufficiently developed reading technique) and if this activity is interesting to him, gives him pleasure. And you can come to such a result only by achieving it thoughtfully and systematically from the very beginning of learning a foreign language.

Today, methodologists, depending on the target setting, distinguish four types of reading: viewing, introductory, studying and searching. Teaching all four of these types is included in the foreign language training program.

Viewing reading involves getting a general idea of the topic and the range of issues addressed in the text. This is a cursory, selective reading, reading the text in blocks for a more detailed acquaintance with its "focusing" details and parts.

If we talk about introductory reading, then it is a cognitive reading, in which the subject of the reader's attention becomes the entire speech work (book, article, story) without the installation of obtaining certain information. This is reading "for yourself", without prior special installation for subsequent use or reproduction of the information received.

Learning reading provides for the fullest and most accurate understanding of all the information contained in the text and its critical comprehension. This is a thoughtful and unhurried reading, involving a purposeful analysis of the content of the text being read, based on the linguistic and logical connections of the text. Its task is to form the learner's ability to independently overcome difficulties in understanding a foreign text. The object of "study" in this type of reading is the information contained in the text, but not the language material.

Speaking of search reading, I would like to note that it is focused on reading newspapers and literature in the specialty. Its purpose is to quickly find well-defined data in the text and in the array of texts (facts, characteristics, descriptions, numerical indicators, instructions).

As for the sequence of types of reading, two options are used in the practice of teaching:

- Introductory - learning - viewing - search;
- Learning - introductory - viewing - search.

The latter option is considered more effective, since it prepares all other types of reading to a greater extent.

It is home reading that combines all the types of reading mentioned above. As for its goals and objectives, it should be noted that, on the one hand, it is the inculcation by students of the skills and abilities of reading literature in a foreign language, and on the other hand, the development of skills and abilities of speech and writing.

Taking into account the interests of students and their level of proficiency in a foreign language, the availability of reading material, as well as some tips available in the methodological literature, the following basic home reading options can be offered for middle-

level students:

1). Individualized home reading, that is, when each student works on his own text, chosen by himself or prompted by the teacher in accordance with his interests.

2). General classroom home reading, that is, when the whole class reads a text that is common to all, but with different tasks and reading settings depending on the language capabilities of the students.

In both variants of independent home reading, there is no need for their topics to correspond to the lexical and conversational topics studied at this stage. At the same time, the topic of home reading should be limited, as a rule, to the approximate topics for oral speech and reading provided for in the curriculum.

On the part of the goal in the organization, two trends have now emerged in the organization of home reading:

1) reading in order to understand the text, that is, actually reading;

2) reading as a preparation for a conversation on what you have read.

This second direction is not the main and constant in the characterization of reading as a type of speech activity. It is brought into reading by the practical orientation of the educational process of teaching foreign languages to the development of oral speech.

Based on the purpose of teaching foreign languages in a modern school, in the organization of home reading, taking into account the above, it is necessary to distinguish two stages. The first stage is actually reading as a process of obtaining information from the text. This stage is mandatory when working on any text. However, at this stage, work on most of the texts proposed by students for independent home reading should end. The second stage is a conversation based on home reading material. This stage of the work should be selective and apply only to a part of the texts or their fragments that are most suitable for speech practice.

At home reading lessons, one should strive to use all types of speech activity: speaking, listening, writing, translation. Two main elements of working with text are present in each lesson:

1) checking reading comprehension

2) the development of oral speech based on what has been read (monologue, dialogue, discussion).

The mentioned techniques (dialogue, discussion) serve to develop and improve students' speaking skills. Speaking is used when discussing what has been read, performing exercises and tasks based on text, that is, when monitoring reading comprehension.

The teacher's work on a home reading lesson begins with the selection of literary material. His correct choice largely determines the further results of the work. When choosing, you need to take into account the following features of students:

1) their interests, determined by age, cultural level;

2) the degree of mastery of the language.

Literary material should be interesting to students, accessible to them for understanding, but at the same time not be primitive. As such material, it is more expedient to choose short novels, short stories, or novellas divided into separate chapters. In this case, at each lesson, you can consider all sides of the selected literary work, carry out all kinds of work on it.

The fundamental requirement for reading texts is their passivity and accessibility for

students. However, the feasibility of the text does not mean lightness. Excessive lightening of the text reduces its educational value. Psychologists note that the most effective is such training in any activity that requires high tension of the individual's psyche, mobilization of his will and attention. It is known that the psyche functions intensely when the performance of an activity is associated with any difficulties. In addition, reading lends itself to self-regulation, that is, the reader himself can facilitate the conditions for performing the activity and thereby ensure the implementation of the task facing him - extracting information. It should also be noted that the feasibility of reading texts is determined not only by the language and life experience of the student, but also by the type of reading for which the text is intended. So texts for introductory reading in general, as methodologists point out, should be much lighter than texts for the student of reading.

Texts for home reading can be more complicated than texts for, for example, a student of reading in class. The student is not limited in time in working on the home text, has the opportunity to use a dictionary or additional literature at his discretion.

Another important requirement for texts is the requirement of the teaching value of the text. The teaching value of the text is understood as its educational, educational and practical value. The practical value is determined by the effectiveness of the text as a means of forming reading skills. The requirements for the language form of reading texts vary depending on the type of reading. Therefore, although the readability of the text is also determined by the amount of language material difficult to understand and unexplored linguistic phenomena, but the implementation of this requirement will be different. First of all, the difficulties of recognizing the studied linguistic phenomena will be determined not by the sound, but by the graphic form. For example, such difficult phenomena for listening, as homophones, are easily identified by the reader, due to the peculiarities of their graphic form: [tu:] - to, two, too. On the contrary, homographs that do not make listening difficult may complicate the understanding of the text when reading: read-[ri:d] and [red]. Taking into account these difficult-to-recognize linguistic phenomena in visual perception and their graduated introduction into texts is especially important at the initial stage, when the reader has no language experience in a foreign language, and he does not know how to use a reasonable linguistic guess. The amount not studied in the texts used in the advanced stages also depends on the type of reading. In texts for introductory reading, only such unfamiliar words can be used, the meaning of which can be guessed, or those whose understanding is not essential to the general meaning of the text. Their number can be 8-10% and even be increased to 20-25% according to individual authors. As for the student of reading, since this type of reading does not exclude the possibility of using a dictionary, the number of unfamiliar words in the texts can be large.

The selection of texts will vary depending on the stage of training. So, at the initial stage it is recommended to offer students only entertaining texts; at the middle and senior - both, but at the middle stage it is desirable to require entertaining texts, at the senior (according to the author - informative). The author strongly recommends using informative, informative texts, bearing in mind that the main thing that defines a text from the point of view of communicative value is the information contained in it.

The use of literary texts in the course of home reading has become firmly established in the practice of teaching foreign languages in secondary school. At the same time, the search for the most rational ways of organizing the selection of artistic material continues.

There are many special manuals, textbook appendices, collections of short stories, fairy tales for home reading. The texts in them are adapted to the secondary school level. But not always anthologies, collections, stories are enough to create a holistic picture of the richness and diversity of the literary fund of the country of the language being studied. There is a need to expand the choice of literature for home reading lessons.

Selivanova N.A. advises to apply a systematic approach to the selection of literary texts for home reading, which will allow students to create a clearer and deeper understanding of the fiction of the country of the language being studied thanks to acquaintance with the works included in the golden fund of national literature: pupils', youth and so-called "adult" literature, beloved by teenagers.

As mentioned above, for home reading it is more expedient to choose short stories and short stories for a more complete and comprehensive acquaintance with them. However, more voluminous works, novels, novellas should also not be ignored, and familiarity with the entire work is optional.

A holistic approach can be provided by a comprehensive reading of the individual parts of the work, in which the sense of the whole is not lost. These parts can be called text fragments. When selecting text fragments, it is necessary to take into account the interest of students in the storyline of the development of the behavior of literary heroes. It is desirable that each text corresponds to a significant moment for the disclosure of the plot conflict. As you know, there are five such key moments: exposition, plot, vicissitudes (development of the action), climax, denouement.

The main criteria for selecting episodes include the following:

- the significance of the episode in the development of the general idea of the work;
- problematic, that is, the presence of a problematic situation in the episode, which serves as an effective incentive to penetrate into the essence of the conflict, increases the motivation of reading, creates a certain psychological mood that promotes the speech activity of students;
- extralinguistic informativeness (we are talking about the subject of a work of art). In this case, the subject is understood not as a circle of events that form the life basis of the works, but those phenomena of reality that make up the essence of what is happening to the characters: moral and ethical themes of good and evil, friendship, love, justice;
- regional value- in some fragments it is necessary to include, if possible, episodes that reveal to students certain phenomena of reality that are peculiar to the country of the language being studied.
- It is important to emphasize that home reading texts can be of different styles and each style is characterized by its own special scheme.

So, the suitability of texts or parts of them for work in a home reading lesson and speech practice with them can be determined by the following criteria:

- 1) a bright and entertaining plot of a text or passage;
- 2) emotionality and imagery of presentation;
- 3) the relevance of the material;
- 4) the thematic proximity of the subject matter to the life experience and interests of students;
- 5) the possibility of various situational transformations of the content of the text or passage.

Depending on the purpose and nature of speech practice, in some cases, its compliance with only two or three of these criteria may be sufficient to determine the suitability of the text.

Now we should move on to the question of practical lessons on home reading in high school; what techniques should be followed so that the home reading lesson becomes entertaining and effective. Let's consider this question on the example of any text.

When composing a task, the text should not be divided into parts so as not to disrupt the overall picture of the work, but in the course of work, the teacher can divide the exercises into two separate lessons at his discretion. Assignments compiled according to the text are divided into two parts: separate assignments for students' homework and assignments for classroom work. The lesson is given time to check home exercises, but with some interpretation. The exercises included in the students' homework are related to working on vocabulary, pronunciation, translation and grammar. There are always tasks to prepare an expressive reading of a certain passage and its literary translation, as well as to memorize the proposed passage by heart. The last task is necessary for the accumulation of speech material in students and for instilling in them the ability to feel a foreign language. When composing exercises for classroom work, it is necessary to take into account the type of speech activity (reading and oral speech), that is, the main attention is paid to checking the general and detailed understanding of the text, as well as speaking. The latter include tasks that begin with the words: describe, comment, compare, etc. Initially, all work begins with the fact that it is necessary to choose a vocabulary, that is, to make an active dictionary for students to expand and deepen their vocabulary. Vocabulary material from the literature on home reading is selected on the basis of the general principles of the selection of vocabulary material based on the available vocabulary minimum of students. These principles include the following:

- 1) the principle of compatibility, that is, the ability of a word to be combined with a large number of words;
- 2) the thematic principle, that is, the importance of the word to express the necessary concepts;
- 3) the principle of stylistic limitlessness, that is, the ability of a word to be used without stylistic restrictions;
- 4) grammatical principle, on the basis of which mainly words that can carry a grammatical function in a sentence are selected.

The selection of active vocabulary is made on the basis of topics for oral speech, which is designed to cover, if possible, fully proposed speech situations that may arise in the process of speech communication.

When composing an active dictionary, it is also useful to include there, in addition to new and partially familiar material (new meanings and new use of lexical units that have already been learned in another meaning, another use or another compatibility), already familiar lexical material, the need for repeated repetition of which is associated with the presence of special language difficulties in it that arise when speaking or understanding.

It should be noted that if home reading is introduced at the initial stage of training, then the lexical material of the selected book should be reduced to the necessary minimum, which is achieved by excluding all words and expressions that are not necessary in the first place to achieve the set learning goals. The development does not include words, although communicatively valuable, but not related to the topics studied at a particular stage of

training, phraseological combinations equivalent in function to the word, synonyms, etc. Since the vocabulary of students is replenished in stages, then at an advanced stage of learning, its expansion can occur not only through the introduction of new lexical units (that is, in breadth), but also by including in it meanings unknown to students or lexico-semantic variants of already familiar words, increasing synonymic and antonymic series, expanding the series equivalents to Russian words, adding derivatives and compound words to the nests of single-root vocabulary, replenishing the dictionary with phraseological splices and phraseological units. When composing exercises, it is customary to take into account the type of speech activity (reading and oral speech) and the language material functioning in each of these types. However, since reading and oral speech are functionally interrelated, reading serves as a source of information for oral speech, and possession of oral speech provides understanding of the text, it can be difficult to draw a clear line between exercises aimed at understanding the text and exercises aimed primarily at speaking when composing exercises.

The following types of exercises are aimed at a deep understanding of the text:

1) exercises aimed at facilitating the understanding of linguistically difficult passages of the book: semantics of difficult words and phrases, identification of unfamiliar words by their word-forming elements and context, translation, analysis of sentences with a complex grammatical structure

2) exercises whose task is to facilitate the perception of extralinguistic information by students: searching for names for individual parts (chapters) or compositional units, substantiating the author's title of chapters or the entire book, questions and answers on the content of the book

Both of these groups of exercises can be by their nature both language and speech exercises, more or less reproducing natural speech communication, in which all language means known to the learner are used. The specifics of the training stage should affect mainly the linguistic content of the exercises, that is, the degree of difficulty of the lexical material and the degree of complexity of grammatical structures. It should be emphasized that at the initial stage of learning, when it is necessary to gradually and in a certain sequence master certain elements of speech and separate actions with separate language units are necessary, the role of language exercises is especially great. At home reading lessons, at the initial stage, prepared speech sounds to a greater extent, since students still lack the skills and abilities to freely use a foreign language. In this regard, the exercises are less creative and should be repeated at certain intervals (only in other versions). At an advanced stage of learning, the role of speech exercises should increase, the approach to them should be more creative, but at the same time we should not forget about language exercises because the assimilation of new elements of speech continues.

After discussing the book in parts, another, third stage of work is needed. This stage is necessary to repeat the vocabulary and control its assimilation, as well as to discuss the content of the entire book. It is planned that the third stage should prepare students to write an essay on the book they have read.

The specificity of the last, final or review stage is that the attention of students is focused mainly on the content of the utterance, and the way of expressing the utterance fades into the background. Speech communication should be as close to natural as possible. Students' statements should be creative. So, if at the beginning of the work on the book their

statements were mainly informative in nature, at the main stage - informative and descriptive with separate elements of subjective assessment, now the element of subjective assessment should become dominant in the statements of students. At this stage, the very nature of the discussion of the book also changes. So, if at the beginning it was about individual actions of the heroes and the motivation of these actions, and the course of events was presented by the students in chronological order or as it was covered in the book, that is, the discussion was more specific and detailed, now it should become more generalizing. The main attention is paid to the nodal issues of the content and systematization of individual thoughts and ideas of the work on the main problems (the characteristics of the actors, the typicality or not typicality of their image, the connection of the work with reality, with the author's worldview, the relevance of the work in our days, the features of composition, plot, language, etc.). The main forms of work here, respectively, should be student messages on individual topics that have a generalizing nature, teacher's questions to students and students to each other, discussion. This lesson can have two options: the first, when students are given questions that have a generalizing character, they prepare messages at home and then a conversation or discussion unfolds in the classroom on the basis of these messages (this option is more appropriate for the initial stage of learning when the student does not speak a foreign language well enough). For the advanced stage of learning, a more creative approach to discussing the book is needed. It consists in the fact that the discussion takes place immediately in the classroom, without preliminary homework (except, perhaps, one thing - to review the entire book from beginning to end and restore all the main events in memory). During the lesson, the teacher gives the right direction to the discussion, offering students questions or setting them certain tasks. It goes without saying that the nature of questions and tasks is directly dependent on the ability of students - their language and general education training. But whichever option the teacher chooses to discuss the book, the ultimate goal should be the same - to bring students to a written statement, since competent command of written speech is the main indicator of a high level of foreign language proficiency.

Reading, being one of the sources of information, occupies a significant place in a person's life. The purpose of reading is to comprehend a visually perceived speech message. The process of reading is the process of perception and active processing of information, graphically encoded according to the system of a language. Learning to read contributes to the implementation of almost all the main aspects of education - mental, moral, aesthetic and labor. It promotes the development of imaginative and logical thinking, imagination, attention, memory.

Of great importance in the possession of a foreign language as a means of communication are home reading lessons. With the correct organization of classes, students develop an artistic taste, they learn to analyze, generalize, and argue.

The teacher's work on home reading lessons begins with the selection of literary material that should be informative and correspond to the age, interests of students and the degree of their language proficiency.

References:

1. Vaisburd M.L. Blokhina S.A. Learning to understand a foreign language text when reading as a search activity // IYASH, 1997, No. 1-2.

2. Kamaeva T.P., Karpova L.V., Deeva IM. Poetry in a foreign language lesson: modern approaches to teaching reading // IYASH. 1996. No. 3.
3. Skrebnev Yu.M. Fundamentals of the stylistics of the English language. Textbook for universities. Moscow: Astrel, AST, 2000. - 224 p.
4. Komissarov V.N. General theory of translation / V.N. Komissarov. - M., 2000. - 253 p.- 253 c.
5. Clark E.V. Universals. Relativity and Language Processing / E. V. Clark, H. H. Clark // Universals of Human Language / Ed. by J. Greenberg. - Stanford: Stanford University Press, 1978. - P. 225-279.
6. Nasibboyeva Mukarrama Salimjonovna. English official style and business correspondence style. International scientific journal "Interpretation and researches" Volume 1 issue 9, p 154.